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FEMINISM IN LITERATURE: AN OVERVIEW

-Rakesh Patel*

The emergence of feminist criticism is abrupt and spontaneous which crosses the all geographic boundaries. I personally consider Doris Lessing to be one of the major feminist writers in the west who is perceptive seeker of the self and of feminine identity. Though there are vague analytical approaches present, there are also some instructions of female studies that pave the way for suggestions regarding book selection that can be taken into consideration for classroom discussion.

Feminist criticism revolves around the analysis of the image of women as we come across in the works of some male authors. It also takes account of existing criticism of female authors. There is prescriptive criticism which deals with setting up some sorts of standards for literature that can broadly be termed as "good" from the feminist point of view. In other words, this prescriptive criticism entails a need for new literature that can meet its standards and can show a path to the authors who are producing literary works from a new feminist view point.

The aspect of feminism in literature is of a great importance when it comes to studying its emergence, causes, and implications into writings. Feminism, more or less, finds its essence and roots in the women's liberation movement and therefore feminist criticism values those writing most which entail the aspects of this movement. In order to elaborate this point, I would like to use Cheri Register's assumption regarding the

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work that can get feminist appreciation if the work entails some of the functions: serve as a forum for women; help to achieve cultural androgyny; provide role models; promote sisterhood; and augment consciousness-raising.¹

The work of literature needs to serve as a forum for women so that there can be space for learning and sharing female experiences. This can greatly be helpful in equilibrating the cultural value systems which has been giving prime importance to the male interests. This can further pave the way for emerging cultural androgyny. Moreover, the work should create role-models so that the sense of feminine identity can be brought forth and this can effectively be done by depicting women who are "self-actualizing, whose identities are not dependent on men."² The character of Bim (Bimla) in Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day* educates herself and becomes self-reliant and succeeds in creating her own identity in the Das household.

The feminist movement attempts to develop and spread the feeling of sisterhood which is a new world of community among women normally aimed at facing steadfast against animosity that most of the women experience for the other women because of their isolation, and feeling of inferiority for their competition for catching male attention. In this respect Virginia Woolf saw the lack of positive female-to-female relationship in literature:

"Chole liked Olivia," I read and then it struck me how immense a change was there. Chole liked Olivia perhaps for the first time in literature. Cleopatra did not like Octavia. And how completely *Antony and Cleopatra* would have been altered had she done so!...All these relationships between women, I thought rapidly recalling the splendid gallery of fictitious women, are too simple. So much has been left out, unattempted."³

The work of literature needs to clearly throw the light on the women-women and women-man relationship

so that the reads, especially women, can identify themselves very closely. The literature need to be so much powerful that suppose the women readers do not identify with the female characters, they should be in a position to empathize with the female characters portrayed in the writing.

So, how to augment "consciousness-raising" in literature? A literary work need to offer realistic and authentic insights into the development of the female personality, relationships with the others, and self-discovery and identity. These are some of the issues we find in the feminist writing today. With the implications of these issues in broad sense, feminism today, not just restricted to the west, has crossed the all geographical boundaries. This is perfectly true with Indian English writings and the writings of the other countries as well.

Indian writing in English is not untouched by feminism. It is an offshoot of the Western feminist movement. There were freedom fighters, the spread of education, economic development, and the resultant awareness in women which can really be called the true impetus to feminism in India. Regional literature also played a vital role in shaping the pattern of feminism in India. Indian literature beautifully presents the image of women crushed beneath the past/traditional restrictions and some aspirant try to break through to see the brave new world. The search for identity has become the core part of feminism in the literature of the world. If you read the feminist literature written in the recent times, you will see that the issue of identity crisis is at the centre because there is inevitable basis difference is observed between man-woman and boy-girl in the contemporary societal structure. If you read the poetry by Kamala Das, the identity crisis and the complexity of man-woman relationship are always there!

Whether it is Indian writing in English or the works of other commonwealth countries, the image of women

portrayed are in a way reflects the writer's emotional vulnerability and isolation. Indian writing in English – poetry, fiction and drams, shows the close affinity with the feminism which deals with identity crisis, and mystified men-women relationships, which lead to the feminine consciousness. There's feminist touch and traits in the characters of Anita Desai that reminds us of Virginia Woolf and in the confessional poetry of Kamalla Das that reminds us of Sylvia Plath.

The vision of feminist criticism needs to be central, neutral and broad rather than falling prey to the pluralism and similar obscurantist conceptions. It needs to serve as an active praxis so that it can produce social awareness in real sense of the term.

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Biography

Rakesh Patel is a poet, freelance writer and teacher. Born on 2 May 1979 in Valsad (Gujarat), India, he took his Masters Degree (M. A.) in English Literature from The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, India. From his schooling, he took interest in creative writing which later on became a driving force for his poetry. Born in a small village in Gujarat, he feels intimacy with nature and much influenced by Romanticists as well as Modernists.